

The Brain Drain Phenomenon in the Healthcare Sector: Investigating the Role of Job Satisfaction and Locus of Control

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Abstract

It is of great significance that healthcare professionals of every country are satisfied with their jobs since a lack of interest in the job caused by poor structure, poor remuneration, infrastructure, standards and logistics could seriously cripple the health of the populace. This study assesses job satisfaction and its influence on brain drain of healthcare professionals in Kwabre East Municipality. The study deployed the cross-sectional research design with 105 participants from selected public hospitals in Kwabre East Municipality. Correlation analysis and linear regression at a significance of $p \leq 0.05$ were used to determine the impact of job satisfaction on brain drain among the healthcare professionals in the selected healthcare facilities. The study concludes that satisfaction with professional support and satisfaction with training has a negative but not significant impact on brain drain. Personal satisfaction and satisfaction with salary and prospect have a negative significant impact on their intention to leave. Workload was also concluded to have a positive significant impact on brain drain. Job satisfaction in the workplace can be improved by investing in the logistic and human resources of the facilities where intrinsic values such as motivation and positive attitude is valued. Locus of control has a negative significant impact on the relationship between job satisfaction and brain drain. The study recommends that managers of healthcare facilities should offer well-coordinated and consistent working conditions and also strive for a competitive compensation package and infrastructure from the government to ensure optimum retention of healthcare professionals.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, Personal Satisfaction, Workload, Training, Salary and Prospects, Professional Support, Brain Drain, Locus of Control.*

JEL Classification codes: J28.

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Introduction

Satisfaction in a working environment has played a significant role in eliciting the work behaviour of employees in Ghanaian healthcare working environments (Akinwale, & George, 2020). It acts as an impulse that drives productivity among the staff and as such any organisation that seeks sustainability and has a competitive edge in a business environment devotes much attention to the job satisfaction of the employees (Coker et al, 2011). Job satisfaction is a major determinant of the well-being of the employees since it elicits the staff to make informed decisions regarding staying

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or leaving their organisation. In the Ghanaian healthcare sector, job satisfaction has been a bone of contention among the healthcare staff, either in government or private hospitals and clinics. Due to the risks and high occupational hazards involved such as the contraction of incurable diseases, being happy in the Ghanaian healthcare sector entails adequate staff motivation to bring about productive work behaviour.

Job satisfaction for healthcare employees has been described as a positive feeling of contentment that individuals obtain from their jobs while working for a corporate organisation (Ezeja et al., 2010; Akinwale, & George, 2020). In other words, employees' job satisfaction describes an attitudinal component of employees towards their job by expressing job satisfaction as the degree to which they like or dislike the job (Akinwale, & George, 2020). Whenever staff enjoy the work they do, they are noticed to be productive and content and such employees usually have a high job satisfaction level. Employees who are not satisfied with their work have low satisfaction with their work and mostly experience stress at the workplace (Ogbolu et al, 2015). Low job satisfaction in the Ghanaian healthcare sector has been attributed to the shortage of personnel, psychosocial pressure and poor remuneration (Fitzpatrick, 2012). Healthcare practitioners mostly have problems with the working conditions, employee voice, employee rights, sense of accomplishment on the job and internal value of the tasks. Edem et al (2017) indicated that job security, employee safety, recognition for best effort and performance, employee safety and working relationship among employees are the major factors that influence the satisfaction of health practitioners in Ghana. It has been asserted that the human resource crisis in the healthcare sector in Ghana characterized by severe emigration is partly due to implementation lapses of certain policies, and this has resulted in a persistent shortage of workers in healthcare facilities (Teye, 2022; Poku, et al., 2023). Employees in the Ghanaian healthcare sector therefore, find the healthcare sector to offer unsuitable working conditions, prone to environmental threats to life, job insecurity and poor remuneration (Edem et al, 2017). This has over the years caused a phenomenon called brain drain where most of the health workers migrate overseas for better working conditions and remuneration.

Brain drain refers to the movement of highly skilled workers from a developing country to a developed country (Ogaboh et al, 2020; Osigbesan, 2021). Brain drain as a phenomenon has drained Africa of healthcare professionals to developed nations with North America and Europe being the prime targets for emigrating health workers. The situation in the Ghanaian healthcare sector keeps worsening as data from the Ghana Registered Nurses and Midwives Association (GRNMA) indicates that more than 3000 nurses and midwives have left the country since the beginning of 2022 (Ghanaian Times, 2023). An article written by the Ghana Broadcasting Corporation (2023) stated that nearly 150 health professionals have left the Pantang Psychiatric Hospital for jobs overseas in the last 6 years. The article further indicated that in March 2023 alone, 11 experienced health professionals, 10 nurses and a doctor resigned from posts in the facility. The World Health Organisation has revealed and cautioned that Ghana is part of the 55 countries that are losing health workers due to international migration (GBC, 2023). The United Kingdom has blacklisted Ghana from being a source of recruitment of healthcare personnel, however, brain drain in the Ghanaian health sector is still high as the pull and push factors remain constant. The shortage of health personnel from brain drain is projected to persist through 2035 if no action is taken (Ghana Health Service, 2020). Chibango (2013) provides evidence to support the claim that highly skilled workers in the health sector from African countries are migrating abroad, particularly those from sub-Saharan Africa. According to the Ghana Health Service (2020) update on the COVID-19 situation it is evident that the need for medical professionals in Africa, in general, is greatest, particularly in Ghana (Adjei-Mensah, 2023). But Ghana is likely to experience a shortage of human resources because of the emigration of medical professionals considering the current agitations emanating from government policies on pensions and other issues. The severe nursing workforce

emigration in Ghana has left the current health sector with low staff morale, and serious nurse specialist workforce shortages, and a high staff-to-population ratio (Asabir, 2018). In effect, the brain drain of healthcare professionals together with poor conditions of services threatens the development process of the healthcare sector in Ghana. Since Ghana needs to retain these personnel in a post-COVID-19 restructuring of the health services across Ghana, there is a need to find out what motivates the health workers who are currently leaving the shores of Ghana (Adjei-Mensah, 2023).

Job satisfaction has been known in literature to be the major cause of brain drain in developing countries like Ghana. However, there are certain factors that go beyond job satisfaction which influence a person to stay or have the intent to migrate. Whereas job satisfaction has been critically looked at as a contributing factor which influences employee retention, its relationship with brain drain is complex and not entirely understood. Research suggests that psychological variables which include the locus of control of the individual could play a critical role in mediating this dynamic (Rotter, 1996). However, there is a lack of empirical studies that examines how job satisfaction indirectly inboxes through locus of control. Without a critical comprehension of this mediating mechanism, interventions that are aimed at reducing talent loss in developing countries like Ghana could prove ineffective or incomplete. This study therefore seeks to address the gap examining the indirect effect of job satisfaction on brain drain through the mediating role of locus of control.

Literature Review

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theoretical basis of this investigation is the theory of planned behaviour, a cognitive theory that links the beliefs of a person to their behavioural patterns (Ajzen, 2020). In the context of this work, this theory provides a basis for understanding why healthcare workers may migrate from Ghana. The theory of planned behaviour is a psychological framework that describes how an individual behaves at any moment in time, based on their belief systems, according to Hamilton et al. (2020). This theory was first developed and introduced by Icek Ajzen in 1985 to describe the psychological basis of behaviour. According to Fan et al. (2021), the theory of planned behaviour stems from the theory of reasoned action, also developed and introduced by Ajzen and Martin Fishbein in the late 1900s. The application of this theory is diverse, including marketing and educational promotions, public and environmental psychology, as well as in the health sector, especially in health psychology (Ulker-Demirel & Ciftci, 2020). The theory of planned behaviour consists of three components, which include attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Ajzen, 2020).

According to Hamilton et al. (2020), the attitude towards the behaviour component of the theory explains how the individual making the action evaluates such actions. This evaluation can be positive or negative and is based solely on how the individual believes the outcome of their actions would be. For instance, a healthcare giver in Ghana who may want to migrate would evaluate the positives and negatives such an action would bring them before concluding. Negative outcomes such as separation from family and immediate environment will be evaluated, and positive outcomes such as improved standard of living, increased salary and prestige will also be evaluated. In the end, according to this component of the theory, these evaluations will shape the attitude of the healthcare giver towards migrating from Ghana.

The second component of the theory is the subjective norm component. According to (Ajzen, 2020), this component of the theory relates to perceived pressure from the social relations and environment of the decision-maker to make one decision or the other. In this instance, the person importance the decision-maker places on what people think about them and the decisions they

make is key. The motivation to act on what these people think is also an important aspect of this component (Conner, 2020). Based on this, a healthcare worker in Ghana, who may have certain expectations from family, friends, and even colleagues at work, may be swayed by such expectations. Their motivation to meet such expectations is also an important point of reference to see through such an action of migrating from the country or not.

The last component of the theory of planned behaviour is the perceived behavioural control component of the theory. According to Bosnjak et al. (2020), this component has to do with how easy or difficult it will be for the decision-maker to carry out an action they have planned or perceived. Similar to the concept of self-efficacy, where a person's belief in their capabilities becomes important for them to reach high-performing heights, the perceived behavioural control is based on the mental strength and resilience of the decision-maker. In an instance where a healthcare giver would want to migrate from Ghana, the components explain how the perceived power of facilitating or impeding factors would influence the behavioural control of such a nurse.

Brain Drain

The issue of brain drain in Ghana has attracted a lot of attention over the past few decades, especially given that Ghana is a developing country that would ordinarily need all of its human resources available and ready to serve in varying capacities in different sectors of the economy. In a review of brain drain in the health sector of Ghana and other mentioned African countries, Dovlo (2004) discovered that training output was a huge limitation factor for the retention of healthcare givers at that time, highlighting the inability of sub-Saharan countries to compete economically with other industrialized countries in the labour market of healthcare workers. The study suggested the establishment of new and relevant educational and training curricula as a possible mitigation strategy. Qi and Chimenya (2015) assert that the basis for brain drain in developing African countries is factors such as unbearable living and working conditions, as well as low wages. These factors act as a form of motivation for such workers to seek better salaries and a safer working and living environment elsewhere. In a reflective analysis, Poku et al. (2023) performed a cross-sectional analysis of the emigration intentions of specialised nurses in Ghana using a sample composition of 225 participants. After assessing the data using descriptive statistics and linear regression, the study found a high mean score for the intention to migrate (mean = 3.43), while the push factors that accounted for such intentions to migrate explained 48.6% of the variations in the model ($R^2 = 0.486$; $F_{(5, 219)} = 38.46$; $p < 0.001$). The findings from these studies highlight the urgent need to continuously understand the issue of brain drain in Africa, especially in Ghana where the health sector plays a significant role in the lives of citizens in the country.

Locus of Control

Locus of control is an individual's belief regarding the causes of his or her experiences and the factors to which that person attributes success or failure (Ogar et al., 2024; Abashiya, 2017). Locus of control as propounded by Rotter (1966) locus of control refers to the extent to which individuals take responsibility for event in their life. In other words, it is how much people believe that their behaviour is influenced by a given situation or, how much a situation is controlled by an external force (Adjei-Mensah, 2023). The locus of control can either be internal or external (Adjei-Mensah, 2023). He further explained that people may be classified along a continuum according to their perception of what controls their life events (Adjei-Mensah, 2023). Rotter used a bipolar dimension to express control from internal to external and not as a typology. Internals tend to attribute outcome of life events to their own control, people who have internal locus of control believe that the outcome of their activities are results of their own abilities (Mamah et al., 20021). They believe that their hard work would lead them to obtain positive outcomes. They also believe that every action has its consequences which makes them accept the fact that things happen and it depends on them if they want to have control over it or not. On the other hand, a person with an external

locus of control attributing his or her success to luck or fate, will be less likely to make the effort needed to work harder (Tella, Tella, & Adeniyi, 2011).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction in an organisation is regarded as an important measure of high productivity and improved work (Aikins, et al., 2023). There is a relationship between staff turnover, non-attendance of employees, workplace accidents and job satisfaction (Aikins, et al., 2023). Job satisfaction is an extremely vital phenomenon of study because globally, it has been established to determine quality care and patient safety (Suleman, Hussain and Shehzad, 2018). According to Locke (1969), job satisfaction is defined as a “pleasurable emotional state of the appraisal of one’s job, as achieving or facilitating one’s job value”. In effect, one who likes his or her work may be considered as having job satisfaction and vice versa (Aikins, et al., 2023). The significance of job satisfaction of nurses on patients’ care, patient satisfaction, patient outcome and general healthcare delivery cannot be over-emphasized, as employee job satisfaction is essential in the daily life of the workforce (Aikins, et al., 2023). It enables employees to satisfy customers/patients. It creates a customer experience at work and reduces employee turnover intention. Furthermore, the concept of satisfaction for healthcare employees has been described as a positive feeling of contentment that individuals obtain from their jobs while working for a corporate organisation (Ezeja et al., 2010; Akinwale, & George, 2020). The significance of job satisfaction of nurses on patients’ care, patient satisfaction, patient outcome and general healthcare delivery cannot be over-emphasized, as employee job satisfaction is essential in the daily life of the workforce (Bani-Hani, & Hamdan-Mansour, 2025).

Satisfied employees seem to be highly creative and dedicated to work; they engage and absorb themselves with the goals and objectives of the organisations (Ogbolu et al., 2015; Akinwale, & George, 2020). In a recent study by Blomberg and Welander (2019), they affirmed that nurses who find happiness and derive satisfaction in their work would have embarked on several years of service in building such satisfaction and passion that drive them to productive work behaviour (Akinwale, & George, 2020). In other words, happiness at work does not come once but accumulates with time consequent upon motivational techniques offered in the workplace (Akinwale, & George, 2020). However, the turnover of nurses and other healthcare workers, in general, can be expensive for the management of healthcare organisations owing to employee engagement, training and retraining (Lorber and Savic, 2012; Akinwale, & George, 2020). Therefore, some healthcare service providers motivate their health workers and ensure they are happy and comfortable with their work and the organisation's surroundings. In this study, several constructs under job satisfaction are examined to determine how they influence brain drain within the healthcare industry in Ghana.

Professional Support

Professional support refers to the degree to which employees’ contributions at organizations are valued, which implies that their associated well-being and capabilities are given full consideration (Alcover et al., 2018; Maan, et al., 2020). Literature also confirm that individuals’ professional support helps boost their obligations toward organization in order to reciprocate favourably. Furthermore, they also want to satisfy their socioemotional needs and incorporate organizational affiliation into their social identity (Maan, et al., 2020). Extant literature has shown that individuals’ professional support enhances both in-role performance such as goal attainment and extra role performance such as helping and supportive behaviour toward coworkers (Alcover et al., 2018; Maan, et al., 2020). Studies indicate that professional support increases job satisfaction, lowers employee turnover and enhances dedication and positive emotions towards the job (Yu and Frenckel, 2013).

Salary and Prospects

Salary is a form of episodic compensation from a firm to its worker, which is completely stated in an employment contract (Chaudhry, et al., 2011). It is weighed with piece wages, where each job, period of job (timings) or other unit is paid distinctly, rather than on a periodic basis (Chaudhry, et al., 2011). All other social factors are important for enhancing and to make job satisfactory for employees are significant but satisfaction from pay is must (Tsigie, 2021). Flaherty and Pappas (2002) critically explored that employee have lower satisfaction and higher turnover intentions when paid a fixed salary (Chaudhry, et al., 2011). Also, salary satisfaction depends on employees' intention about job safety or prospect where the employee feels secured with the job at hand and has access to readily available opportunities elsewhere. A study by Wahab (2014) indicated that intention to work overseas by highly skilled workers include factors such as salary and compensation. Another study by Bertoni et al., (2023) indicated that skilled healthcare professionals with higher willingness to take risks for competitive salary and job prospects are more likely to migrate abroad.

Workload

Workload is often used to describe situations in which an individual's expected performance goals are not met. Task complexity increases when performance falls short of these expectations. According to Wickens et al. (2012), there isn't necessarily a negative correlation between increased workload and poor results. There are situations where performance can be enhanced by adding more tasks. Nevertheless, this is mostly observed in workplaces with a propensity for light workloads. Wherein the combination of weariness or boredom will negatively impact worker performance. However, studies have shown that good patient happiness, high-quality nursing services, nurse job satisfaction, high nurse efficiency, cost efficiency, and favourable rates of occupancy can all result from nurses working at their ideal workload (Alghamdi, 2016). The dwindling number of healthcare professionals keeps the staff to population ratio in the Ghanaian context at large which increases workload on the present practicing workers.

Personal Satisfaction

Job satisfaction represents a person's evaluation of his/her job and work context (Staw and Ross, 1985). It is the positive emotional state that arises from an individual's assessment of their work, their affective response to their work, and their attitude towards their work. Research has demonstrated that an employee's age, gender, and degree of education affect their level of devotion to their workplace and level of pleasure (Hackman and Oldham, 1980; Hickson and Oshagbemi, 1999). Additionally, dispositional elements like personality, affectivity, and self-efficacy have an impact on their levels of intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction (Franek and Vecera, 2008). For instance, Franek and Vecera (2008) indicated that a strong sense of efficacy enhances human satisfaction and personal well-being in many ways and that people who doubt their capabilities shy away from difficult tasks, which they view as personal threats (Kraftová, & Kraft, 2008). Therefore, the contentment and personality of the individual influences the desire to be open to new prospects or remain where they are.

Training

Training is defined as a planned learning experience designed to bring about permanent change in an individual's knowledge, attitudes, or skills (Costen and Salazar, 2011; Tekleab, 2018). The benefits and value of training are undeniably pivotal to an organization's success through maintaining high standards and consistency as well as keeping abreast of the fast-changing external environment (He, Findley, & Wheatley, 2018). Training affects trainees' attitudes and behaviors at workplace if they apply newly learned knowledge and skills on the job (He, Findley, & Wheatley, 2018). When employees feel they are valued by their organizations, they are motivated to do their

best at work and obliged to reciprocate through means, such as modifying their behaviors and performing the tasks the way they are trained (American Psychological Association, 2012; He, Findley, & Wheatley, 2018). It should be pointed out that employees are more likely to experience job satisfaction when they are provided with well-designed training courses conducted by knowledgeable and professional trainers (Choos and Bowley, 2007; Tekleab, 2018). Thus, with effective training, employees exhibit proper behavior on the job following training instructions and produce higher job satisfaction (Tekleab, 2018). Quality of training and practice can therefore influence employees' job satisfaction which could trigger their intention to migrate.

Methods

Research Design and Setting

The cross-sectional descriptive design was chosen to assess the impact of job satisfaction on brain drain in the health sector since it is significant in gathering data from multiple sources at a point in time without influencing variables that are being observed in the study. The focus of the study was healthcare facilities in the Kwabre East Municipal Area. Kwabre East Municipality has 10 health centres, 1 government hospital and 4 clinics with 7 doctors, 5 physician assistants and 349 nurses and other health professionals (KEMA, 2023). The study randomly selected three public hospitals in Kwabre East Municipality and they included Mamponteng Health Centre (46 health professionals), Kenyase Health Centre (49 health professionals), Abirem Health Centre (47 health professionals).

Study Population

The study focused mainly on all health professionals in the selected public healthcare facilities in Kwabre East Municipality. The study included health professionals who have worked in the health sector for over a year. The health professionals were chosen from various departments in the facilities which include family planning units, labour wards, obstetric emergency units, out-patient department, antenatal care unit, obstetric theatre and recovery ward and gynaecological wards. Health professionals who had managerial or administrative duties were exempted together with those that were on leave.

Sampling and Sample Size

Slovin's (1991) sample size determination technique is used to obtain the overall sample size for the study, as shown in equation 1.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)} \quad (1)$$

Where;

n= sample size of participants.

N= population of participants.

e= error term.

$$n = \frac{142}{(1+[142*0.05^2])} = 105 \quad (2)$$

From the algorithm in equation 2 above;

n =105 healthcare professionals

The 105 participants were conveniently sampled from the selected public hospitals.

Data Collection and Analysis

The participants for this study were informed about the intent of the study and those that consented were selected for the study. The questionnaires were administered to the participants and the answered questionnaires were taken immediately after completion. The study further used IBM SPSS v27 to analyse the data gathered. The data was cleaned by configuring the frequencies of each item as a confirmation of data accuracy. Descriptive statistics such as standard deviation, frequencies and means were used to ascertain the level of job satisfaction and agreement to two statements on brain drain. Correlation analysis was used to establish the relationship between workload, personal satisfaction, satisfaction with prospects, prospects, salary, standards and brain drain. The study further used linear regression from SPSS PROCESS v4.3 at a significance of $p \leq 0.05$ to determine the mediating impact locus of control on the relationship between job satisfaction and brain drain among the healthcare professionals in the selected healthcare facilities.

Measure

The study adapted validated scales for the collection of data. The Measure of Job Satisfaction instrument designed by Traynor and Wade (1993) was adapted to measure the job satisfaction of the healthcare professionals of the selected public hospitals in Kumasi Metropolis. Job satisfaction has 5 sub-themes which include workload (6 elements), personal satisfaction (6 elements), satisfaction with professional support (6 elements), satisfaction with salary and prospect (6 elements), and satisfaction with training (4 elements). Personal satisfaction, satisfaction with salary and prospect, satisfaction with training, and satisfaction with professional support were designed with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly dissatisfied' to (5) 'strongly satisfied'. Workload was designed with a Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly agree' to (5) 'strongly disagree' to measure the level of workload of the healthcare professionals. Validity and reliability tests were conducted to assess the internal consistency of the instrument. Also, items (4) under locus of control were adopted from Nieben et al.'s, (2022) Internal-External Locus of Control Short Scale. Also, items to measure brain drain was adopted from Mobley et al. (1978) intention to emigrate scale which consists of three items. The internal consistency for this scale in other studies were over 0.80 (Labrague et al., 2020).

Table 1. Convergent Validity and Reliability Analysis of Constructs

Main Variables	Specific Variables	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	KMO	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity
Salary and Prospect	The amount of pay I receive	0.556	0.824	0.811	Chi-square=210.894 P=0.000
	The degree to which I am paid fairly for my contribution	0.539			
	My prospect for promotion	0.616			
	How secure things look for me in the future of the organization	0.520			
	My job security	0.546			
	The opportunities I have to advance my career	0.422			
Satisfaction with Professional Support	The amount of time spent on administration	0.581	0.868	0.835	Chi-square=287.481 P=0.000
	The amount of support and guidance I receive from my supervisor	0.649			
	The opportunities I have to discuss my concerns	0.664			

	The support available to me in my job	0.618			
	The overall quality of the supervision I receive in my work	0.677			
	The degree of respect and fair treatment I receive from my superior	0.467			
Personal satisfaction	Feeling of worthwhile accomplishment from my work	0.469	0.808	0.734	Chi-square=198.027 P=0.000
	The extent to which I can use my skills	0.488			
	The extent to which my job is varied and interesting	0.595			
	The standard of care given to patients	0.484			
	Amount of personal growth and development gotten from my work	0.618			
	Quality of my work with patients	0.412			
Satisfaction with training	Opportunity to attend courses	0.767	0.877	0.713	Chi-square= 108.592 p=0.000
	Time off to attend courses	0.816			
	Funding for courses	0.759			
	Extent of adequate training for what I do	0.716			
Workload	There is ample time available to go through my work	0.575	0.915	0.893	Chi-square= 410.455; p-value= 0.000
	There is ample time available to finish everything I do	0.682			
	There is ample time available for patient care	0.796			
	Workload matches my energy level	0.742			
	There is adequate number of staff	0.709			
	I am able to adequately care for my patients	0.707			
Brain Drain	I often think of leaving this organization	0.571	0.812	0.628	Chi-square= 132.736; p-value= 0.000
	If I could choose again, I would not work for this organization	0.854			
	I intend to look for new opportunities outside the country in the nearest future	0.771			
Locus of Control	I am my own boss	0.527	0.758	0.715	Chi-square= 105.9; p-value= 0.000
	If I work hard, I will succeed	0.593			
	Whether at work or in my private life; what I do is mainly determined by others	0.709			
	Fate often gets in the way of my plans	0.499			

Factor loading values for the items reported under Table 1 show that the items for satisfaction with salary and prospect, satisfaction with professional support, personal satisfaction, satisfaction with professional support, workload and brain drain were all over 0.4 which indicates that the items for each item were a good measure for their respective constructs. Also, the Cronbach's Alpha scores for each construct were over 0.7 indicating that there is a robust internal consistency for the constructs. Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant at 1% for each construct which indicates that

the relationship between the variables was significant. Overall, the scores given in the reliability test indicate that the instrument was very reliable.

Results

The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants, validity and reliability tests, correlation analysis and regression results are presented in this section. Table 2 below presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents;

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Items	Frequency	Percentages
Sex	Male	11	10.5
	Female	94	89.5
Age	Less than 25 years	13	12.4
	26-35 years	61	58.1
	35-45 years	24	22.9
	46-60 years	7	6.7
Marital status	Single	46	43.8
	Married	46	43.8
	Separated	11	10.5
	Divorced	2	1.9
Education	Certificate	41	39.0
	Diploma	44	41.9
	Bachelors	13	12.4
	Master of nursing/midwifery	7	6.7
Years of experience	1-3 years	27	25.7
	4-6 years	49	46.7
	7-9 years	23	21.9
	10 years and over	6	5.7

As presented in Table 1, out of the 105 participants, 11 (29.5%) were males and 94 (70.5%) were females. Also, the majority of the respondents (n=74; 70.5%) were less than 35 years. Also, 46 (43.8%) were single, 46 (43.8%) were married, 11 (10.5%) were separated and 2 (1.9%) had divorced. With regards to academic qualifications, most of the participants were certificates (n=41; 39%) and diploma holders (n=44; 41.9%). Majority of the participants (n=76; 72.4%) had between 1-6 years of experience.

Job Satisfaction of Health Professionals

The level of satisfaction among the health professionals is presented in Table 3 with composite mean scores for each construct of job satisfaction. The composite mean scores for the constructs include; satisfaction with professional support (n= 2.2), personal satisfaction (n= 2.0), satisfaction with training (n= 1.98), satisfaction with salary and prospect (n= 2.02), workload (n= 2.2). The composite mean scores for all the predictors of job satisfaction were very low depicting lower satisfaction levels among the health professionals.

Table 3. Level of Job Satisfaction

Variables	Composite mean	Standard Deviation
Satisfaction with professional support	2.20	.909
Personal satisfaction	2.00	.765
Satisfaction with training	1.98	.805

Satisfaction with salary and prospect	2.02	.788
Workload	2.20	1.058

The Impact of Job Satisfaction on Brain Drain

The study deployed the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis to examine the relationship among the variables used. The results indicated in Table 4 shows that there is a strong significant correlation between all the predictors of job satisfaction indicating that all the items are strongly related. Also, brain drain was found to have a weak significant negative relationship with satisfaction with professional support ($r = -.226, p < .021$), personal satisfaction ($r = -.400, p < 0.000$), training ($r = -.320, p < 0.000$), salary ($r = -.455, p < 0.000$) and a weak not significant negative relationship with workload ($r = -.054, p < .584$). Locus of control was also found to have a weak significant negative relationship with brain drain ($r = -.384, p < 0.000$).

Table 4. Pearson Correlation Analysis

	Professional Support	Personal Satisfaction	Training	Salary and Prospect	Workload	Brain Drain	Locus of Control
Professional Support	1						
Personal satisfaction	.375**	1					
Training	.274**	.468**	1				
Salary and Prospect	.300**	.456**	.603**	1			
Workload	.277**	.445**	.441**	.405**	1		
Brain Drain	-.226*	-.400**	-.320**	-.455**	-.054	1	
Locus of Control	.303**	.951**	.478**	.397**	.425**	-.384**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It can be seen from Table 5 that job satisfaction has a negative significant impact on brain drain. Therefore, a unit increase in job satisfaction decreases brain drain by 34.36%. Also, locus of control was found to have a negative significant impact on brain drain. As such, a unit increase in locus of control decreases brain drain by 34.68%.

Table 5. Effect of Job Satisfaction on Brain Drain

Item	Coeff.	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
_cons	3.9523	.2628	15.0367	.000	3.4310	4.4737
Job satisfaction	-3.4364	.5438	-6.3190	.000	-2.3577	-4.5151
Locus of Control	-3.4679	.4933	-7.0300	.000	-4.4464	-2.4894

Dependent Variable= Brain Drain (Intent to Migrate)
r= 0.6224
f= 32.2417
p= 0.000

Mediating Effect of Locus of Control on the Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Brain Drain

From the results, the indirect effect of job satisfaction on brain drain via mediator locus of control has a calculated point effect of -3.7739. This indicates that locus of control has a negative significant impact on the relationship between job satisfaction and brain drain. Therefore, for each unit increase in job satisfaction, the intent to migrate decreases by 3.8 units through the mediating role

of locus of control. Therefore, the negative indirect effect means that higher job satisfaction leads to lesser brain drain (intention to migrate), however, this happens though not directly, through changes in the locus of control of a person. People that are satisfied with jobs develop stronger internal locus of control and feel more empowered or have much control over their career choices. This strong internal sense of control makes them less likely to leave. Therefore, job satisfaction alone is not enough to prevent brain drain as it helps by shaping the perception of people on the control they have over their future and work. Enforcing this sense of control is significant to keeping talent.

Table 6. Mediation Analysis

Direct Effect						
Effect	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	c_cs
-.0819	0.0130	-6.3190	0.0000	2.3577	4.5151	3.0630
Indirect Effect						
Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI			
-3.7739	0.6397	-4.9306	-2.4294			

Discussion

The issue of brain drain cannot be overlooked, and the impact it has on the socioeconomic well-being of individuals in developing countries cannot be overstated. Such an issue inhibits greatly the intellectual capacity – a component that is vital for innovation and growth – of the country. Brain drain is especially important given that developing nations such as Ghana are already grappling with infrastructure, and are constantly faced with difficulties relating to education, technology and healthcare. It was ascertained that components of job satisfaction such as personal satisfaction, satisfaction with salary and prospect, and workload had a significant and negative impact on brain drain. These findings are corroborated by several research studies in extant literature. According to Torrisi and Pernagallo (2020), the negative association between job satisfaction and brain drain can be reduced and possibly eliminated through favourable streamlined procedures, a merit-based reward and promotion process, and functional research productivity. These actions would go a long way to improve the reputation and status of the healthcare sector in Ghana, and would as well reduce the propensity to migrate for health professionals in the country.

According to Najib et al. (2019), personal satisfaction is affected by socioeconomic and other political factors such as corruption, political instability and poor governance as these factors affect the trust and belief a person has in the institutions within which they work at any given time. This encourages them to seek stability elsewhere, where their satisfaction needs will be met through stability and safety. In the view of Okafor and Chimereze (2020), the challenges relating to satisfaction for health professionals are unique and especially glaring in the sense of the high patient-nurse ratio, and limited facilities. These are obvious limitations throughout the healthcare facilities within Ghana, and especially within the Kwabre East Municipality which is not one of the major hubs in the country. These limitations lead to frustrations and burnout and serve as a reason to migrate for such a healthcare worker. The improvement of these conditions would go a long way to encouraging health professionals to stay and serve in Ghana. According to Hashish and Ashour (2020), the establishment of a fair compensation scheme would also be an encouragement for such workers. In this instance, because the healthcare professionals work in the Kwabre East Municipality where infrastructure is lacking, allowances, in the form of compensation, can be given to them on a monthly basis to compensate for the extra work they would have to put in due to the nonexistence or lack of certain vital infrastructure.

Salaries and career prospects are significant factors that influence brain drain among healthcare professionals in developing countries (Gautam & Aryal, 2018). The demanding nature of their work, coupled with the low wage structure leads to financial dissatisfaction, which encourages most of these healthcare professionals to migrate in search of greener pastures. According to Kadel and Bhandari (2019), nurses, midwives, and other healthcare workers are known to work longer hours under very challenging circumstances regularly. For such an individual, the substantial wage gap between Ghana and say, the USA or the United Kingdom, for healthcare workers will be a very strong incentive to encourage a migration from them. This way, they will be in a favourable position, financially, to provide for themselves and their families. Likupe (2013) has shown that in developing countries, there are usually limited opportunities to grow careers through advanced training and specialization. A scenario such as that in the Kwabre East enclave could lead to an increased sense of stagnation and a lack of fulfilment. In the face of a lack of such opportunities, healthcare professionals are compelled to seek them elsewhere in other countries. In the view of Ajayi et al. (2022), the establishment of proper working conditions, as well as career-developing opportunities and incentives such as paid study leave will prove essential in retaining such workers in the country.

The continued existence of brain drain is a limitation factor that hampers the achievement of sustainable development goals in Ghana. The results of this study will improve the knowledge of brain drain and job satisfaction in Ghana, especially in the Kwabre East Municipality. The understanding will provide the basis to deploy better policy frameworks aimed at reducing the number of healthcare workers who leave the country regularly to seek better conditions elsewhere. It could also be an extension to even attract back others who had left for reasons related to job satisfaction. This will go a long way to enhance the development of the health sector in Ghana and the general well-being of the citizens.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Nurses and midwives in the Ghanaian healthcare sector have been facing very challenging working environments (Poku et al., 2023). This study has shown that the satisfaction level of practicing healthcare professionals is not adequate enough a trigger in pull and push factors of emigration could cause them to leave. The study concludes that satisfaction with professional support and satisfaction with training has a negative but not significant impact on brain drain. Personal satisfaction and satisfaction with salary and prospect have a negative significant impact on their intention to leave. Workload was also concluded to have a positive significant impact on brain drain. Locus of control has a negative significant impact on the relationship between job satisfaction and brain drain.

Job satisfaction in the workplace can be improved by investing in the logistic and human resources of the facilities where intrinsic values such as motivation and positive attitude is valued. Managers of healthcare facilities should offer well-coordinated and consistent working conditions and also strive for a competitive compensation package and infrastructure from the government to ensure optimum retention of healthcare professionals. These are significant since compensation or salary alone is not a yardstick for the satisfaction of healthcare professionals. It is imperative for health administrators to exhibit prominent leadership qualities and offer support to elevate the professional status of healthcare professionals in Kwabre East Municipality.

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